

RELATIONSHIP OF FATIGUE AND FRACTURE TO MICROSTRUCTURE AND PROCESSING

IN Al_2O_3 FIBER REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Summary

The tensile and fatigue properties of three matrices, including commercially pure magnesium, ZE41A (Mg-4.25Zn-0.5Zr-1.25RE), and Al3Li, containing 35 vol pct FP Al_2O_3 fibers were studied as a function of orientation between the loading and fiber axes, matrix composition, fiber volume fraction, and fiber/matrix interfacial chemistry. It was found that the axial properties were controlled by the fiber strength, and the orientation dependence of tensile strength could be analyzed in terms of the critical strains to fracture parallel and normal to the fibers. Matrix chemistry modifications had little influence on fiber strength but significantly increased the matrix and interface strengths. A transition from fiber controlled fracture to matrix/interface controlled fracture was found as the angle between the loading axis and fiber direction was rotated from zero to 90 deg. As the matrix and interface strengths increased, a transition in fracture from across fibers to parallel to the fibers was delayed. Off-axis fatigue properties were primarily controlled by the matrix and/or interface strengths. Little benefit was achieved by increasing the vol pct fibers from 35 to 55, unless the fibers were involved in the fracture process. The interfacial reaction zone was identified as MgO in the Mg-base composites and LiAl_5O_8 in the Al3Li composite.

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Introduction

Although it is generally recognized that fiber, matrix, and interface properties play a role in controlling the mechanical behavior of metal matrix composites, limited opportunities have been available to systematically vary these parameters as part of a research program. This paper is one of a series (1-4) that have evolved from a continuing study of the relationship of fatigue and fracture mechanisms to the microstructures and processing histories of FP Al₂O₃ fiber-reinforced magnesium and aluminum alloys. Previous results from this program have been reported on (a) the influence of fiber volume fraction and orientation on the tensile and fatigue behavior of commercially pure magnesium (1); (b) the effect of alloying the magnesium matrix at the 55 vol pct fiber level (2); (c) the factors controlling unstable off-axis fracture of commercially pure magnesium (3); and (d) the influence of contact time with liquid magnesium on the extent of the fiber/matrix reaction zone (4).

These results have now been extended to include a direct comparison of the orientation dependence of the mechanical properties of composites with three matrices (i.e., commercially-pure Mg, alloyed Mg, and Al-3 wt pct Li) at the 35 vol pct fiber level. These data, in conjunction with the earlier reported data at a fiber volume fraction of 55 pct, have provided the basis for identifying the conditions under which the fibers, matrix and/or interface control the properties, and are the subject of this paper.

Experimental

Composite plates manufactured by E. I. DuPont de Nemours and Co. by liquid infiltration of FP Al₂O₃ fibers have been employed in this program. The plates contained either 35 or 55 vol pct of continuous, unidirectional, 20 μ m diameter Al₂O₃ fibers in a matrix of commercially pure magnesium (CPMg), ZE41A (a magnesium alloy with approximately 4.25 wt pct Zn, 0.5 wt pct Zr, and 1.25 wt pct rare earths), or an aluminum three percent lithium alloy (Al3Li).

The specimens, utilized for both tensile and fatigue testing, were 15.2 cm long with 1.27 cm x 0.25 cm rectangular cross sections. Machining was performed with the Al₂O₃ fibers oriented at 0, 22.5, 45, and 90 deg to the tensile axis. Aluminum tabs were bonded to both sides of the specimens' ends for gripping purposes.

The tensile and fatigue tests were performed at room temperature in a closed-loop hydraulic testing system. The fatigue tests were run under load control at a load ratio of 0.1 and a frequency of 10 Hz. Tests which did not result in failure in 1 to 2 x 10⁶ cycles were terminated. The tensile tests were performed under displacement control at a strain rate of 8.3x10⁻⁵s⁻¹. Specimen strain was determined from strain gages attached to opposite faces of the tensile specimens.

The detailed microstructure of the composites, including the constituents and morphology of the fiber/matrix reaction zone, was characterized with conventional light microscopy, transmission electron microscopy, and Auger electron spectroscopy. Fracture surfaces of both tensile and fatigue specimens were characterized by scanning electron microscopy.

Results

The tensile and fatigue results for ZE41A and Al3Li with 35 vol pct fiber, which have not been reported elsewhere, are featured in this section. Analogous results for CPMg with 35 and 55 vol pct fiber and ZE41A with 55 vol pct fiber have been reported (1,2) and, therefore, they are not emphasized here. The previous results are extensively referred to, however, throughout the remainder of this paper.

Tensile Behavior

The results of the tensile tests of the 35 vol pct fiber materials are presented in Table I and Figures 1 and 2*. As was previously observed in CPMg (1), fiber orientation affected the tensile behavior of both the ZE41A and the Al3Li materials. The ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and elastic modulus (E) were found to decrease as the misorientation angle between the fibers and the loading axis increased while the strain to failure (ϵ_f) initially increased, reaching a maximum at a fiber orientation of 45 degrees, and then decreased for larger misorientations. ZE41A and Al3Li showed a similar dependence of UTS on fiber orientation with the ZE41A material exhibiting a slightly higher UTS at all orientations. Both materials were superior to the CPMg, which showed a slightly stronger orientation dependence. The elastic modulus of ZE41A was similar to that of CPMg at all fiber orientations. The elastic modulus of Al3Li was similar to CPMg and ZE41A at zero degrees but substantially higher than both for off-axis loading. At intermediate angles, Al3Li exhibited the highest elongation and CPMg had the lowest. Similar elongations were observed in all three materials under axial and transverse loadings.

Table I. Average Tensile Properties of 35 Vol Pct Al₂O₃ Fiber Reinforced ZE41A and Al3Li

Matrix Material	Orientation, Deg.	UTS, MPa	E, GPa	ϵ_f , Pct
ZE41A	0 (axial)	438 (445)	163 (164)	0.29
ZE41A	22.5	301	127	0.63
ZE41A	45	234	97	0.99
ZE41A	90 (transverse)	190	83	0.53
Al3Li	0 (axial)	377 (441)	165 (186)	0.29
Al3Li	22.5	247	158	1.14
Al3Li	45	199	147	1.78
Al3Li	90 (transverse)	142	126	0.34
CPMg	0 (axial)	383 (396)	149 (164)	0.26
CPMg	22.5	207	116	0.52
CPMg	45	108	90	0.45
CPMg	90 (transverse)	104	85	0.42

Values in parentheses are calculated from the rule-of-mixtures.

* The tensile results for Al3Li are similar to the results obtained by Champion et al. (5) on equivalent material.

Figure 1 - Effect of fiber orientation on ultimate tensile strength for commercially pure magnesium, ZE41A, and Al3Li matrix materials with 35 vol pct fiber. Data for 55 vol pct ZE41A from Reference 2 is also included.

Figure 2 - Effect of fiber orientation on failure strain for commercially pure magnesium, ZE41A, and Al3Li matrix materials with 35 vol pct fiber.

Fractographic characterization of the tensile specimens indicated that failure of the ZE41A and Al3Li axial specimens occurred at 90 deg to the applied stress, i.e., through the fibers, as observed in CPMg (1) and 55 vol pct ZE41A (2). Failure of the 22.5 deg specimens also occurred primarily across the fibers at approximately 90 deg to the applied stress. At 45 deg mixed mode failure was observed with a combination of failure across the fibers, as in axial failure, and along the fibers occurring. Failure of the transverse specimens was along the fiber direction and occurred by a combination of matrix and interfacial failure. Comparison of typical fractographs from CPMg, ZE41A, and Al3Li transverse tensile specimens, Figure 3, shows the increasing degree of matrix failure as one goes from CPMg to ZE41A to Al3Li.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3 - Scanning electron micrographs of typical transverse tensile failures in Al₂O₃ fiber reinforced (a) CPMg, (b) ZE41A, and (c) Al3Li.

Fatigue Behavior

The fatigue results for ZE41A and Al3Li containing 35 vol pct fiber are presented in Figures 4 and 5, respectively. Results for CPMg are included in each figure for comparative purposes. A comparison of 35 and 55 vol pct fiber ZE41A is provided in Figure 6. When loaded axially or at 22.5 deg, the higher slope of the ZE41A S-N curves resulted in endurance limits (10^6 cycles to failure) which were equivalent to CPMg, even though the UTS of ZE41A was considerably higher than CPMg. When loaded at 45 and 90 deg the ZE41A had an endurance limit that was 65 to 70 percent above that of CPMg. The Al3Li had a fatigue resistance identical to CPMg when loaded axially. Considerable improvement over CPMg was observed, however, for all off-axis orientations of Al3Li. Comparison of the ZE41A and Al3Li data indicates that at 0 and 90 deg the two materials exhibit similar endurance limits while at 22.5 and 45 deg the Al3Li exhibits an endurance limit that is higher than ZE41A.

The fatigue and overload regions of axial and 22.5 deg ZE41A and Al3Li fatigue specimens exhibited fractographic features similar to those of the axial and 22.5 deg tensile specimens. In all cases cracking occurred across the fibers at approximately 90 deg to the tensile axis. The features of the fatigue and overload failures were so similar that it was difficult to differentiate between the two. Subtle differences in the amount of matrix ductility, fiber pullout, and interface decohesion were observed, however.

The transition in fracture morphology from failure across fibers at 22.5 deg to mixed mode failure at 45 deg to failure along the fiber direction at 90 deg, which was observed in the tensile specimens, was also present in the fatigue specimens. However, as observed in off-axis CPMg specimens (1), the morphologies of the fatigue and overload regions of the 45 and 90 deg ZE41A and Al3Li specimens were different. The differences in ZE41A are

Figure 4 - Effect of fiber orientation and matrix chemistry on the fatigue behavior of 35 vol pct fiber materials.

Figure 5 - Effect of fiber orientation and matrix chemistry on the fatigue behavior of 35 vol pct fiber materials.

Figure 6 - Effect of fiber orientation and fiber volume fraction on the fatigue behavior of Al₂O₃ fiber reinforced ZE41A. 55 vol pct data from Reference 2.

illustrated by the fractographs of Figure 7. The overload regions exhibited features identical to those of the corresponding tensile specimens, as would be expected. Fatigue cracking, on the other hand, occurred along the direction of the fiber axis by a combination of delamination of the fiber/matrix interface and cracking of the ZE41A matrix. Of these, matrix cracking, which exhibited a brittle, crystallographic morphology, as in Figure 7b, was the predominant mode. The differences between overload and fatigue failure in Al3Li are illustrated by the fractographs of Figure 8. Although the

(a)

(b)

Figure 7 - Scanning electron micrographs of typical (a) overload and (b) fatigue failures in 45 deg specimens of Al₂O₃ fiber reinforced ZE41A. Note that the overload failure occurs almost exclusively along fiber/matrix interfaces while subcritical fatigue crack growth occurs parallel to the interfaces but primarily through the matrix.

Figure 8 - Scanning electron micrographs of typical (a) overload and (b) fatigue failures in 45 deg specimens of Al_2O_3 fiber reinforced Al_3Li .

overload and fatigue failures both occurred primarily through the matrix and parallel to the fiber direction, the overload failure typically exhibited a smoother matrix failure while the fatigue failure contained numerous undulations running roughly perpendicular to the fiber direction. The undulations were similar in appearance to coarse fatigue striations.

Reaction Zone Characterization

Previous transmission electron microscopy and Auger spectroscopy studies have shown that the fiber/matrix reaction zone in both CPMg and ZE41A is composed of MgO particles and that interfacial failure occurs between the metallic matrix and the MgO reaction zone (1,2). Based on the results of that characterization, it was concluded that the interfacial strengthening observed in ZE41A was due to an increase in the size of the reaction zone and/or a change in the size and spacing of the MgO crystals and not any change in the chemical nature of the reaction zone.

Transmission electron microscopy of the Al_3Li composite indicated the presence of a fiber/matrix reaction zone which varied in thickness from approximately 0.05 to 1.0 μm , Figure 9. Microdiffraction analysis of the reaction zone, Figure 10, identified it as being primarily cubic LiAl_5O_8 spinel. Prewo, using electron diffraction, has also identified the reaction zone as a spinel (6). However, X-ray diffraction measurements of extracted fibers have identified the presence of lithium aluminate, LiAlO_2 (5,7). The reaction zone was found to penetrate preferentially along grain boundaries in the Al_2O_3 fiber, as at location 1 in Figure 9. Thick sections of reaction zone often contained Al_2O_3 grains encased in the reaction product, location 2 in Figure 9.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9 - Transmission electron micrographs of the fiber/matrix reaction zone in Al₃Li. The various constituents are indicated by: Al (Al₃Li matrix); RZ (reaction zone product); and FP (Al₂O₃ fiber). Note the large variation in reaction zone thickness.

(a)

(b)

Figure 10 - Electron diffraction patterns taken from reaction zone particles. Cubic 100 zone axis in (a) and 211 zone axis in (b).

Interfacial Modification

It has been postulated that the larger reaction zone and hence the higher interfacial strength in ZE41A, compared to CPMg, results from a longer contact time with the highly reactive liquid matrix. To test this hypothesis, samples of CPMg were heat treated above the melting point of the matrix (650°C). Table II gives the details of the thermal exposures.

Table II. Thermal Exposure Parameters for CPMg

<u>Specimen</u>	<u>Exposure Temperature</u>	<u>Exposure Time</u>
AR	--	--
TE1	675°C	15 min.
TE2	725°C	15 min.
TE3	725°C	30 min.

Fractographs of the as-received specimen (AR) and the specimen exposed at 725°C for 15 minutes (TE2) are presented in Figure 11. It can be seen that the fracture path in AR was almost exclusively through the Mg/MgO interface, as discussed previously (1). The fracture surface in TE2, however, showed a considerable amount of matrix failure. The amount of matrix failure generally increased with exposure time and temperature. These observations were corroborated by the Auger data in Figure 12. The fine structure of the magnesium peaks taken from a fiber trough (Figure 12a) and a fiber surface (Figure 12b) in as-received material are typical of metallic magnesium and MgO, respectively (8). Thus, failure in AR occurred along the matrix/reaction zone interface with very little of the matrix adhering to the reaction zone. However, as the degree of thermal exposure was increased, magnesium peaks from exposed fiber surfaces showed a gradual transition toward a fine structure typical of metallic magnesium (Figures 12 c-e). Hence, a trend toward a greater amount of matrix material adhering to the MgO particles of the reaction zone as the reaction is allowed to proceed is indicated. TEM observations confirm that the increase in matrix adhesion occurs in conjunction with an increase in the MgO particle size (4).

Discussion

The tensile results of this and previous studies (1,2) indicate that Al₂O₃ fiber reinforced CPMg and ZE41A tested in the axial direction respond to changes in fiber content in much the same manner as other composite systems (9-11), i.e., strength and modulus increase with increased fiber content. This behavior is consistent with the trend predicted by the rule of mixtures (ROM). The ROM provided a reasonable prediction of the UTS and E for ZE41A and UTS for CPMg; however, it overpredicted the E for CPMg and the UTS and E for Al₃Li. The ROM calculations were made using UTS and E for Mg equal to 90 MPa and 45 GPa (12), respectively; UTS and E for ZE41A equal to 165 MPa and 45 GPa (13), respectively; UTS and E for Al₃Li equal to 160 MPa and 80 GPa (5,14), respectively; and UTS and E for Al₂O₃ equal to 965 MPa and 384 GPa (15), respectively.

The off-axis results illustrate the dramatic effect that fiber orientation can have in composites of this type. Large drops in UTS and E were observed with increasing orientation in all three materials. In the transverse

(a) Overall fracture surface of as-received CPMg material.

(b) Fiber surface in as-received CPMg material.

(c) Overall fracture surface of CPMg material held at 725°C for 15 minutes.

(d) Fiber surface in CPMg material held at 725°C for 15 minutes.

Figure 11 - Fractography of selected Al_2O_3 fiber reinforced CPMg specimens.

(a) Trough in as-received CPMg material.

(b) Fiber surface in as-received CPMg material.

(c) Fiber surface in CPMg material held at 675°C for 15 minutes.

Figure 12 - Expanded view of Mg peak in Auger electron spectra of fracture surfaces for all materials studied.

(d) Fiber surface in CPMg material held at 725°C for 15 minutes.

(e) Fiber surface in CPMg material held at 725°C for 30 minutes.

Figure 12 (continued) - Expanded view of Mg peak in Auger electron spectra of fracture surfaces for all materials studied.

direction the UTS in each material had dropped to a value approximately equal to that of the matrix alone. The modulus, however, was increased by approximately 40-45 GPa in each material by the presence of the fibers. The strain to failure was also a strong function of fiber orientation.

The results also indicate the strong effect that matrix composition has on off-axis composite behavior. The use of ZE41A or Al3Li as the matrix material in place of CPMg produced substantial increases in off-axis UTS and in the failure strain at intermediate orientations. Use of Al3Li also produced an increase in the elastic modulus of off-axis specimens. With one apparent exception, namely the UTS of ZE41A specimens, matrix composition had little effect on axial properties. The change in UTS observed in ZE41A is thought to be due to variations in processing rather than direct matrix effects since for 55 vol pct fiber the ZE41A UTS was lower than CPMg (2) while for 35 vol pct fiber the opposite was true.

The effect of matrix composition on composite behavior can be more easily understood if one considers that the properties of a composite material are determined by a combination of the fiber, matrix, and interfacial properties. It is also necessary to consider that failure may occur by one or more of a number of mechanisms and that it may be either stress or strain controlled. In general, axial strength, both static and cyclic, is primarily dependent on the fiber volume fraction and the fiber properties. Matrix properties play only a secondary role. On the other hand, transverse strength is more heavily influenced by the matrix and interfacial properties. At intermediate angles the component controlling failure is controlled by the relative magnitudes of the shear and normal stresses or strains that each component experiences as well as the strengths or critical strains of each component. In general, matrix chemistry can affect all three of the parameters that control composite behavior, i.e., fiber, matrix, and interfacial properties.

Considering first a stress controlled failure process, resolution of the stresses into the fiber axis, interface normal, and interface shear components yields (16):

$$\sigma_{11} = \sigma_A \cos^2 \theta \quad [1]$$

$$\sigma_{22} = \sigma_A \sin^2 \theta \quad [2]$$

$$\sigma_{12} = \frac{\sigma_A}{2} \sin \theta \cos \theta \quad [3]$$

respectively, where σ_A is the applied stress and θ is the angle between the applied stress and the fiber axis. A plot of normalized stress vs angle is given in Figure 13. If failure by fracture across the fibers, which was observed up to 22.5 deg in ZE41A and Al3Li, was a stress controlled failure process, the composite tensile strength would be expected to increase with misorientation angle. This clearly was not observed in these materials. Interfacial failure, if controlled by a combination of shear and normal stresses as indicated by critical stress intensity calculations for CPMg (3), would cause the UTS to fall with increasing angle. This is consistent with both the actual UTS behavior and the observed increase in the fraction of interfacial failure with increasing angle.

Failure may also be considered as a strain controlled process with each failure mode having a unique failure strain. For simplicity we will consider only two failure modes—failure across the fibers and failure along the fiber direction. We will also assume that fiber failure is controlled by the strain along the fiber axis, ϵ_{11} , and that failure along the fiber direction, i.e., the combination of interfacial delamination and matrix failure, is controlled by the strain normal to the fiber, ϵ_{22} . The strain components can be written as

$$\epsilon_{11} = \epsilon_{xx} \cos^2 \theta + \epsilon_{yy} \sin^2 \theta \quad [4]$$

$$\epsilon_{22} = \epsilon_{yy} \cos^2 \theta + \epsilon_{xx} \sin^2 \theta \quad [5]$$

$$\epsilon_{12} = -\epsilon_{yy} \sin \theta \cos \theta + \epsilon_{xx} \sin \theta \cos \theta \quad [6]$$

where ϵ_{11} , ϵ_{22} , and ϵ_{12} are the fiber axis, interface normal, and interface shear components, respectively, and x , y , and θ are as illustrated in Figures 13 and 14.

Figure 13 - Variation of material axes' stresses in unidirectional composite plotted against load direction (Reference 16).

Figure 14 - Variation of strain to failure vs load direction assuming fiber fracture occurs when a critical fiber strain, $\epsilon_{11} = \epsilon^*_0$, is achieved and interfacial delamination occurs when a critical fiber normal strain, $\epsilon_{22} = \epsilon^*_{90}$, is achieved.

The critical strain for fiber fracture, which was assumed to be the axial fiber strain, is related to ϵ_{xx} and ϵ_{yy} by

$$\epsilon_{11} = \epsilon_{xx} \cos^2 \theta + \epsilon_{yy} \sin^2 \theta = \epsilon^*_0 \quad [7]$$

where ϵ^*_0 is the critical fracture strain of the fiber. At $\theta = 0$ Eq. [7] simplifies to

$$\epsilon_{11} = \epsilon_{xx} = \epsilon^*_0 \quad [8]$$

Solving Eq. [7] for ϵ_{xx} yields

$$\epsilon_{xx} = \epsilon^*_0 / \cos^2 \theta \left(1 + \frac{\epsilon_{yy}}{\epsilon_{xx}} \tan^2 \theta \right) \quad [9]$$

For elastic strains $\epsilon_{yy}/\epsilon_{xx} \approx -0.3$ and for plastic strains $\epsilon_{yy}/\epsilon_{xx} \approx -0.5$.

In the same manner, the critical strain for failure along the fiber axis, assumed as the fiber normal stress, is related to ϵ_{xx} and ϵ_{yy} by

$$\epsilon_{22} = \epsilon_{yy} \cos^2 \theta + \epsilon_{xx} \sin^2 \theta = \epsilon^*_{90} \quad [10]$$

where ϵ^*_{90} is the critical fracture strain normal to the fiber. Solving Eq. [10] for ϵ_{xx} yields

$$\epsilon_{xx} = \epsilon^*_{90} / \sin^2 \theta \left(1 + \frac{\epsilon_{yy}}{\epsilon_{xx}} \cot^2 \theta \right) \quad [11]$$

A plot of the tensile failure strain, ϵ_{xx} , calculated from Eqs. [9] and [11] vs angle is presented in Figure 14. For $\epsilon^*_0 = \epsilon^*_{90}$ and $\epsilon_{yy}/\epsilon_{xx} = -0.4$ a transition in failure mode at 45 deg from fracture across fibers to fracture along the fibers is predicted. Further, the strain to failure is expected to rise up to 45 deg reaching a maximum of $3.3 \epsilon^*_0$ and then decrease as θ increases beyond 45 deg. Decreasing ϵ^*_{90} for constant ϵ^*_0 is shown to reduce the maximum strain and shift the failure mode transition to smaller angles. Although ϵ^*_0 and ϵ^*_{90} are not precisely equal for the composites studied, the predicted behavior of Figure 14 is both qualitatively and quantitatively similar to the observed behavior in Figure 2. The actual failure strains of ZE41A and Al3Li peak at 45 deg, which also corresponds to the angle at which the failure mode transitions are observed, at values of $3.4 \epsilon^*_0$ and $6.1 \epsilon^*_0$, respectively. Although the above analyses are admittedly simplified in that they do not deal with the effect of two or more failure modes occurring simultaneously or the effect of complex stress interactions, they do, nonetheless, provide a basis from which matrix chemistry effects can be discussed.

The use of ZE41A as a matrix material in place of CPMg provides an increase in both the matrix strength and the interfacial strength (2) and does not significantly affect the fiber strength*. The increased matrix

* Although fiber strength was degraded in the 55 vol pct ZE41A, it was not in the 35 vol pct material. It was therefore concluded that processing variations and not matrix alloy additions were responsible for the reduced fiber strength.

strength results from solid solution strengthening and possibly some precipitation hardening. The increased interfacial strength results from a geometrical rather than a chemical strengthening, as demonstrated by the results of the thermal treatment experiments performed on CPMg. The transverse fracture morphology suggests that Al₃Li also provides an increased interfacial strength, as well as an increased matrix strength, and no large change in the fiber strength (5). For the case of Al₃Li, however, interfacial strengthening is the result of a chemical change in the reaction zone from MgO to LiAl₅O₈ rather than a geometrical change*, as in ZE41A. Thus, both ZE41A and Al₃Li yield increased interfacial and matrix strengths with little reduction in fiber strength.

Since axial failure is controlled primarily by the fiber strength, the axial strengths of the three materials should be similar, as was observed. Whether stress or strain controlled, the onset of failure along the fiber direction should occur at higher angles, however, due to the higher matrix and interfacial strengths of Al₃Li and ZE41A. Furthermore, when failure along the fiber direction does occur it should do so at higher stresses and strains.

To summarize the discussion thus far, the matrix chemistry changes result in an increased matrix and interfacial strength with little change in the fiber strength. These results, which are consistent with the differences in tensile behavior between CPMg and ZE41A and Al₃Li, can also be used to explain some of the differences in fatigue behavior. Under axial loading the fibers bear most of the load and present the primary barrier to fatigue. Thus, since the 35 vol pct fiber materials had similar fiber strengths, they would be expected to have similar fatigue resistances. Similarly, a reduced fiber strength in the 55 vol pct ZE41A was found to yield a reduced fatigue resistance (2).

In an earlier study of CPMg, it was concluded that both the fiber/matrix interface strength and the matrix strength play primary roles in determining off-axis S-N behavior (1). Hence, ZE41A and Al₃Li should both have off-axis fatigue resistance superior to that of CPMg. This was found to be the case for Al₃Li at all misorientations and for ZE41A at 45 and 90 deg. ZE41A at 22.5 deg, however, had a fatigue resistance which was slightly superior to CPMg at intermediate stresses but only equivalent to CPMg as the endurance limit was approached. This was not the case in a comparison of 55 vol pct material in which the ZE41A at 22.5 deg performed considerably better than CPMg (2). An explanation for the variation in behavior of ZE41A at 22.5 deg is not evident at present.

The matrix composition, or more specifically the interfacial strength, was also found to affect the dependence of off-axis behavior, both fatigue and tensile, on fiber content. The off-axis fatigue and tensile behavior of CPMg, in which the fibers were not directly involved in the failure process, was relatively insensitive to changes in fiber volume fraction. On the other hand, the fatigue and tensile behavior of ZE41A at 22.5 deg, an angle at which fiber fracture was involved in failure, was improved by an increase in fiber content. These observations suggest that the off-axis strengths do not benefit greatly from increases in fiber volume fraction unless the fibers participate in failure.

* Geometrical strengthening was ruled out for the Al₃Li because of the smooth nature of the reaction zone/matrix interface.

Conclusions

1. Axial, tensile and fatigue properties of the three composites (CPMg, ZE41A and Al3Li) were primarily controlled by the fiber strength.
2. The orientation dependence of the tensile properties can be described in terms of the critical strains to fracture parallel and normal to the fibers.
3. The off-axis fatigue properties were controlled by the matrix and fiber/matrix interface strengths at 45 and 90 deg for all three composites and at 22.5 deg for CPMg. In these instances subcritical fatigue crack initiation and growth occurred parallel to the fibers. For axial orientations for all three materials and at 22.5 deg for ZE41A and Al3Li, fatigue cracking occurred across the fibers and normal to the loading axis.
4. Matrix chemistry modifications had little influence on fiber strength but significantly increased the matrix and interfacial strengths. Fiber-matrix reaction zones consisted of MgO and LiAl₅O₈ spinel in the magnesium- and aluminum-base matrices, respectively.
5. An increase in the fiber volume fraction from 35 to 55 vol pct increased the tensile and fatigue properties only when the fibers were involved in the fracture process.

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